

LOGISTICS-DRIVEN RETAIL CLUSTERING FOR OPTIMAL URBAN CONSOLIDATION CENTER PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT: *Urban freight transport is vital for city logistics but also contributes to congestion and environmental issues. Urban Consolidation Centers (UCCs) offer a promising way to streamline last-mile deliveries and reduce these impacts. This research aims to determine the optimal location for UCCs by first identifying clusters of retail stores within an urban area. These clusters form the basis for selecting the most suitable UCC sites. The research includes defining clustering criteria for logistics optimization, developing related mathematical models, creating a real-data-based case study, coding the method in Python, selecting UCCs based on clusters, and evaluating the clustering criteria. The findings will support more efficient and sustainable urban logistics.*

KEYWORDS: *location optimization, retail clustering, urban logistics, mathematical modeling, data-driven decision making*

1 INTRODUCTION

Urban areas face increasing challenges in balancing freight transport efficiency with reducing congestion and environmental impacts. The growth of e-commerce and urbanization intensifies pressure on last-mile delivery. UCCs offer a promising solution by centralizing shipments and minimizing unnecessary trips, but their effectiveness depends on optimal city placement. This research addresses that need through a data-driven method that clusters retail stores and applies logistics optimization to identify ideal UCC locations.

The goal is to find the optimal sites of UCCs that improve delivery efficiency and reduce negative urban impacts including sustainability aspects based on greenhouse gas emission. The methodology includes clustering stores using geographic and logistical criteria, developing evaluation models, and implementing the approach with real-world data in Python.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a systematic literature review, which summarized the research background of UCC-related problems. Section 3 describes the potential clustering aspects of stores in an urban area (for example in a downtown). Section 4 presents the mathematical model of clustering-based optimization of UCC's locations, while Section 5 discusses the computational results. Concluding

remarks, limitations and future research directions are discussed in Section 6.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, we are identifying research gaps with a systematic literature review. This section includes three subsections as follows: descriptive analysis of available articles, content analysis, and the consequences.

2.1 Descriptive analysis

To search the Scopus database, we used the "urban consolidation centers" keyword. Initially, this search resulted in 171 articles. We then refined the selection using the following keywords: (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("urban consolidation centers")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE, "j")) OR LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE, "p")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "cp")). We also included only journal articles published in English, reducing the total to 134 articles. Our search was conducted in June 2025, so additional relevant articles may have been published since then.

The reduced articles can be classified depending on the subject area. Figure 1 shows the classification of these 134 articles considering ten subject areas. This classification shows that the majority are on social sciences, engineering, business, decision sciences, computer science, economics, mathematics, environmental science, and energy.

These subject areas highlight the multidisciplinary nature of research works related to UCCs.

Fig. 1 Classification of articles considering subject areas based on a search in Scopus database using topic: “urban consolidation centers”.

As Figure 2 demonstrates, the research on urban consolidation centers has been published in the past 5 years. The number of published papers has increased in recent years which shows the importance of this research field.

Fig. 2 Classification of articles by year of publication based on search in Scopus.

We have analyzed the published articles from the Scopus keywords point of view. We have analyzed the distribution of articles in the following categories: city logistics, urban consolidation, urban freight transport, logistics, sustainable development, last-mile, urban planning, decision making, vehicle routing, stakeholders, optimization, benchmarking and traffic congestions.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the categories. As the categories show, the design and operation of urban consolidation centers is based on multidisciplinary, where optimization, decision

making, organization, and environmental impact are integrated.

Fig. 3 Distribution of papers according to Scopus keywords.

In the following step, the 134 articles were reduced after reading them. We excluded articles whose topic did not fit our interest and did not address the optimization of urban consolidation centers.

2.2 Content analysis

Binh et al. [1] explores public support for Urban Consolidation Centres in Hanoi by analyzing perceptions among key stakeholders through a structured survey. It finds that expected improvements in transport organization positively influence support for UCCs, while concerns about road safety and implementation barriers have little effect. This study primarily contributes a qualitative understanding of social acceptance toward UCCs in a developing urban context. In contrast, our research builds on this foundation by introducing a quantitative approach to determine optimal UCC locations. It incorporates clustering of retail stores, logistics optimization models, and a Python-based implementation using real-world data. Compared to the first study, our approach offers a more advanced, data-driven framework that moves from public perception to practical application, significantly extending the scope of analysis.

An Edinburgh-based study by Akgün et al. [2] focuses on understanding retailer attitudes toward UCCs, emphasizing the role of supportive policies and value-added services. It reveals that most retailers are reluctant to adopt UCCs voluntarily, as their logistics needs are already met by existing service providers. However, external pressures such as regulations or increased costs could make UCC usage more acceptable, provided comparable

services are offered. In contrast, our research work takes a broader stakeholder approach by assessing public support for UCC implementation in Hanoi, including perspectives from transport companies, authorities, and researchers. Our work identifies perceived system-level benefits as key drivers of support. Together, the two studies highlight different but complementary aspects of UCC adoption: our approach focuses on overall public backing, while the other addresses specific conditions under which retailers might engage.

A case study by Thiermann et al. [3] explores proximity logistics in Düsseldorf as a response to logistics sprawl, highlighting how UCCs can function effectively without being located in expensive inner-city areas. It focuses on operational aspects, showing that nearby logistics facilities can support last-mile services like cargo-bike deliveries and stockholding. The study emphasizes the strategic role of existing infrastructure and the involvement of municipal governments in enabling sustainable freight systems. In contrast, our research work addresses the spatial optimization of UCC locations using data-driven clustering techniques based on retail store distribution. While the Düsseldorf study demonstrates feasibility through a real-world service model, our work contributes a mathematical and computational framework for guiding future UCC placement.

Crotti et al. [4] investigates how environmental policies and corporate social responsibility strategies affect competition among logistics service providers in urban freight, using a theoretical market model. It highlights that in competitive markets, eco-friendly CSR strategies and city-imposed pollution charges can encourage providers to adopt UCC services. However, in less competitive settings, stronger CSR incentives are needed to shift behavior toward sustainable last-mile solutions. In contrast, our research takes a practical, data-driven approach by identifying optimal UCC locations through clustering of retail stores and logistics modeling. While the CSR study emphasizes market dynamics and strategic behavior under policy influence, our work focuses on spatial planning and implementation tools to support sustainability. Together, these studies cover both the strategic and operational dimensions of UCC deployment, offering a more comprehensive understanding of how to promote greener city logistics.

Dupas et al. [5] addresses the shift from direct to joint parcel deliveries in city centers, evaluating a two-tier distribution system that includes UCCs, warehouses, and proximity logistics spaces. It aims to optimize both cost and environmental impact by modeling various scenarios that differ in UCC

capacity, truck speed, and delivery configurations. The results show that UCCs can significantly reduce both total costs and CO₂ emissions when properly scaled to match demand. Similarly, our research also focuses on UCC optimization but approaches it through clustering retail store locations and applying mathematical models to identify ideal UCC sites. While the Bordeaux study evaluates different operational scenarios through simulation, our work goes much further by developing a comprehensive, data-driven methodology that includes clustering criteria, real-data case studies, and a coded Python tool to systematically select optimal UCC locations.

Mepparambath et al., [6] explores the effects of UCCs and off-hour deliveries (OHD) on freight flows to retail districts in Singapore, using a combination of behavioral surveys and agent-based simulation. It analyzes the participation likelihood of various stakeholders and assesses how these initiatives influence traffic, load factors, and parking demand in a congested urban area. The study highlights that achieving sufficient participation levels is critical for UCC effectiveness, while OHD impacts delivery patterns differently. In contrast, our research focuses on identifying optimal UCC locations by clustering retail stores and applying mathematical optimization models supported by real-world data and Python implementation. Unlike the Singapore study, which emphasizes behavioral responses and simulation of freight flows, our work provides a more comprehensive and practical framework for the strategic placement of UCCs.

Giampoldaki et al. [7] provides a comprehensive review of UCCs, focusing on their characteristics, services, operational benefits, and key factors affecting their long-term viability. Using a hybrid method of systematic literature review and multiple case studies, it identifies success drivers, common failures, and strategic, tactical, and operational elements crucial for effective UCC management. In contrast, our research goes beyond a review by developing a practical, data-driven approach to determine optimal UCC locations through clustering and mathematical modeling.

Friedrich and Elbert [8] develop advanced optimization models to analyze how city toll regulations influence vehicle routing and the use of UCCs by logistics providers. It incorporates complex factors like heterogeneous fleets, multiple trips, and trade-offs between cost and speed, validated through computational experiments. The results suggest that toll schemes can encourage UCC use and reduce truck entries in urban areas, but high transshipment fees may discourage providers with large delivery volumes. In comparison, our research focuses more on spatial clustering and optimal location selection

for UCCs, providing a practical, data-driven framework rather than detailed operational cost modeling.

Arrieta-Prieto et al. [9] addresses the challenges of urban deliveries exacerbated by online shopping growth, focusing on Urban Micro-Consolidation Centers (UMCs) as a way to reduce congestion and pollution. It presents a complex optimization model and a heuristic solution tested in a Manhattan case study, demonstrating practical benefits for urban freight planning. In contrast, our research emphasizes identifying optimal UCC locations using clustering and mathematical modeling with real-world data and Python implementation. While the UMC study focuses on last-mile delivery optimization and policy implications, our work provides a broader spatial decision-making framework for sustainable urban logistics. Thus, our research offers a more comprehensive, data-driven approach to UCC placement beyond operational route optimization.

Dreischerf and Buijs [10] examine the real-world impacts of introducing UCCs on logistics processes, costs, and service levels across multiple suppliers' distribution networks. The findings reveal that UCCs affect various actors differently depending on the initial network structure and that cost savings are not guaranteed, especially in the short term. In contrast, your research develops a data-driven, optimization-based approach to determine the best locations for UCCs using clustering and mathematical modeling. While this study offers practical insights into operational challenges and stakeholder experiences, our work provides a more comprehensive and systematic framework for planning UCC placement.

Rudolph et al. [11] develops a multi-criteria decision-making approach using AHP and PROMETHEE to identify suitable locations for UMCs, considering demand, land use, and road type. Applied to Stuttgart with real logistics data, it shows how different weighting scenarios influence the number and placement of UMCs. In contrast, our research focuses specifically on clustering retail stores and optimizing UCC locations using mathematical models and Python coding for more systematic site selection.

2.3 Conclusions of literature review

As a summary of the literature review, it can be concluded that our study significantly advances the field by developing a quantitative, data-driven framework for identifying optimal UCC locations through retail store clustering and mathematical modeling. Unlike previous works that focus mainly on qualitative insights or isolated case studies, our research integrates real-world data with a Python-

based implementation to enable practical and systematic site selection. This novel approach facilitates scalable and evidence-based decision-making for urban logistics planning. Overall, our study provides a comprehensive tool that enhances the efficiency and sustainability of urban freight distribution.

3 POTENTIAL CLUSTERING CRITERIA

In a UCC-based supply chain, stores can be clustered according to various criteria, depending on the specific objective of the clustering process, such as optimization, cost reduction, or faster delivery times. The following section presents some of the possible criteria that can be used to form such clusters.

3.1 Clustering based on geographical proximity

Clustering based on geographical proximity aims to group together stores that are located near each other, along with the most suitable UCCs. The primary goal of this approach is to reduce logistics costs, optimize delivery times, and increase overall efficiency. Stores and UCCs located close to one another can be more easily connected, enabling faster and more cost-effective transportation. By considering geographical proximity, UCCs can be established in locations that offer optimal accessibility to the targeted group of stores. This clustering can reduce transportation costs due to shorter travel distances, lead to shorter delivery times, thereby improving service levels and enable better utilization of transport resources. For example, in a city with multiple large retail stores, each is connected to a different but nearby UCC. This setup reduces the distances between stores and consolidation centers, allowing for quicker and more economical deliveries.

3.2 Clustering based on product types or categories

Clustering based on product types or categories involves grouping stores and warehouses according to the characteristics of the products they handle, such as similarities in their product assortments. Stores that sell the same types or categories of goods can be organized into the same cluster. This approach enables transportation processes to better align with specific product requirements and allows UCCs to be located in positions that provide optimal logistics services to the assigned stores. This clustering can support a logistics system optimized according to product categories, help avoid the extra costs associated with transporting highly diverse product

types, and allow better alignment of inventory and transportation needs. For example, stores that sell electronic products and the UCCs serving them can be grouped together, while clothing stores can form a separate cluster. Since electronic items often require special handling, this clustering method makes it easier to provide tailored logistics solutions by selecting appropriate UCCs.

3.3 Clustering based on demand characteristics

Clustering based on demand characteristics aims to group together stores and their corresponding UCCs according to similar demand patterns. This allows for more efficient logistics planning, as predictable demand trends make it easier to schedule timely restocking and optimize deliveries. The basis for clustering can include seasonal demand, daily fluctuations, or weekly demand cycles. This clustering enables more predictable and accurate demand forecasting, facilitates optimal inventory management and transportation planning, and helps reduce logistics and inventory-related costs. For example, if certain stores experience higher sales volumes on specific days of the week, they can be clustered together, while others with different but consistent demand patterns can form separate groups. Based on this clustering, UCCs can be selected and located to ensure faster service during peak demand periods.

Clustering based on seasonal demand patterns focuses on grouping stores and UCCs that experience similar fluctuations in customer demand throughout the year. This enables better anticipation of peak and low-demand periods, supporting more efficient inventory planning and transportation scheduling. Their advantages are the followings: improved forecasting for seasonal demand variations, effective management of seasonal peaks and downturns, and more efficient planning of stock levels and deliveries. For example, during the Christmas season, toy stores require intensified logistical support, whereas stores selling products with lower seasonal sensitivity may not. By clustering stores with similar seasonal patterns, UCCs can be designated and prepared to respond effectively to changing demand conditions.

3.4 Clustering based on capacity and inventory turnover

This clustering approach focuses on grouping high-turnover stores with UCCs capable of handling frequent stock replenishments. Stores with high inventory turnover rates sell products quickly,

requiring their associated UCCs to have greater inventory handling capacities. Clustering based on these characteristics ensures efficient stock management tailored to demand dynamics. This clustering can support the optimization of inventory control and warehousing operations, improve response to changes in demand, and increase capacity utilization across the supply chain. In high-demand, stores, such as grocery retailers, can be clustered with high-capacity UCCs that can support rapid inventory turnover. In contrast, stores with lower demand can be linked to smaller UCCs with less frequent replenishment needs.

3.5 Clustering based on service level and priority

Clustering based on service level and priority involves grouping stores and UCCs that require high service standards or urgent deliveries. By assigning the most suitable UCCs to these clusters, the system ensures that high-priority demands are met quickly and efficiently. The advantages of this clustering are the followings: fast response to urgent delivery needs, quicker service for the most critical stores, and enhanced overall service quality. If a store urgently needs to restock, a direct and well-planned connection with an appropriate UCC ensures that the delivery can be completed promptly, supporting high service levels and customer satisfaction.

3.6 Clustering based on store types or formats

Different types of retail outlets (hypermarkets, small convenience stores, or online shops) have distinct logistics requirements. This clustering approach aims to group stores based on their formats, enabling the design of UCCs that cater to their specific operational needs. By aligning the logistics processes with the business type, supply chain efficiency and service quality can be significantly improved. This clustering can lead to logistics systems tailored to store formats, improved efficiency and cost optimization for different retail structures, and delivery solutions adapted to store-specific needs. Hypermarkets and small convenience stores require different logistics strategies. Hypermarkets may need large-volume deliveries at lower frequency, while small stores often require smaller, more frequent shipments. Clustering them separately allows UCCs to provide services aligned with these operational differences.

The general layout of UCC-based last-mile delivery is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 General layout of an UCC-based last-mile logistics solution including locations (customers), cluster centers (centroids) and UCC.

4 MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The input parameters of the optimization model of the clustering of UCC-based last-mile delivery (retail clustering) are the followings:

- position of locations (stores, companies, and private customers): x_i^L and y_i^L , where $i = 1 \dots i_{max}$,
- position of potential UCC locations: x_j^U and y_j^U , where $j = 1 \dots j_{max}$,
- position of cluster centers (centroids): x_k^C and y_k^C , where $k = 1 \dots k_{max}$,
- length of transportation route between location i and cluster center k : $r_{ik}^{LC}(x_i^L, y_i^L, x_k^C, y_k^C)$,
- length of transportation route between cluster center k and UCC j : $r_{kj}^{CU}(x_k^C, y_k^C, x_j^U, y_j^U)$.

We can define a wide range of objective functions. Equation (1) defines the first objective function as the minimization of total transportation length. Equation (2) defines the second objective function, which is the total freight transport work. Equation (3) defines the third, sustainability-related objective function, which is the total energy consumption depending on the length of transportation routes and the truckload. Equation (4) defines the fourth, sustainability-related objective function, which is the total greenhouse gas emission

depending on the energy consumption and energy source. Equation (5) defines the fifth, economy-related objective function, which is the total transportation cost.

It is possible to define a wide range of constraints, depending on the predefined conditions. Equation (6) describes the first constraint, which defines that it is allowed to assign exactly one cluster to each location. Equation (7) describes the second constraint, which defines a predefined upper and lower limit of cluster size, and it is not allowed to exceed these limits. Equation (8) describes the third constraint, which defines a predefined upper and lower limit of distributed quantity of products assigned to each cluster, and it is not allowed to exceed these limits.

The application of these constraints ensures balanced and feasible clustering. Constraint (6) guarantees that each location is assigned to one and only one cluster, while constraints (7) and (8) enforce that both the number of locations per cluster and the total distributed product quantities remain within predefined upper and lower bounds, maintaining operational limits and resource capacities.

The decision variable of the clustering problem is an assignment matrix, which can be noted as follows: $A = [a_{ik}]$, where a_{ik} is a binary variable.

$$O_I = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{i_{max}} \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} (a_{ik} \cdot r_{ik}^{LC}) \right] + \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} r_{k_{jopt}}^{CU} \rightarrow \min. \quad (1)$$

$$O_{II} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{i_{max}} \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} (a_{ik} \cdot r_{ik}^{LC} \cdot q_i) \right] + \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} r_{k_{jopt}}^{CU} \cdot q_k^{CUM} \rightarrow \min. \quad (2)$$

$$O_{III} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{i_{max}} \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} (a_{ik} \cdot r_{ik}^{LC} \cdot en(q_i)) \right] + \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} r_{k_{jopt}}^{CU} \cdot en(q_k^{CUM}) \rightarrow \min. \quad (3)$$

$$O_{IV} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{i_{max}} \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} (a_{ik} \cdot r_{ik}^{LC} \cdot em(q_i)) \right] + \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} r_{k_{jopt}}^{CU} \cdot em(q_k^{CUM}) \rightarrow \min. \quad (4)$$

$$O_V = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{i_{max}} \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} (a_{ik} \cdot r_{ik}^{LC} \cdot c(q_i)) \right] + \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} r_{k_{jopt}}^{CU} \cdot c(q_k^{CUM}) \rightarrow \min. \quad (5)$$

$$\forall i: \sum_{k=1}^{k_{max}} a_{ik} = 1 \quad (6)$$

$$\forall k: \delta_{min} \leq \sum_{i=1}^{i_{max}} a_{ik} \leq \delta_{max} \quad (7)$$

$$\forall k: \gamma_{min} \leq \sum_{i=1}^{i_{max}} a_{ik} \cdot q_i \leq \gamma_{max} \quad (8)$$

When clustering locations are based on geographical distances, k-means clustering is particularly effective. This is because k-means is inherently a spatial clustering algorithm that minimizes the sum of squared distances between each point and the centroid of its cluster. It is well-suited for problems where Euclidean distance is a meaningful metric, such as physical distance on a map. As a result, k-means naturally forms geographically compact clusters, which is highly relevant in logistics for minimizing transportation costs and travel times. Figure 5 shows the pseudocode of Lloyd's k-means clustering, which was used in our scenario analysis.

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1: choose k as the number of centroids
2: randomly assign all points to a centroid
3: calculate the centroids as mean of their assigned points
4: repeat
    4a: reassign each datapoint to its closest centroid
    4b: recalculate centroids as mean over their assigned datapoints
5: until convergence
    
```

Fig. 5 Pseudocode of Lloyd's k-Means clustering [12].

However, in cases where clustering is based on non-spatial attributes, such as product types, demand characteristics or demand pattern, inventory turnover, service level and priority or location type, the objective is not necessarily spatial compactness but rather similarity in operational or business features. In these scenarios, the clustering task can often be framed as a classical center selection problem, where the goal is to find a representative or "central" profile (e.g., a typical demand pattern or

store format) for each cluster. These problems can often be solved using optimization models, such as:

- p-median: to minimize the total distance between each item and its assigned center,
- k-medoids or hierarchical clustering: where the center is a real observation and similarity is based on domain-specific attributes,
- mixed-integer programming: when clustering is part of a broader decision problem, such as warehouse assignment or inventory pooling.

It means, that in the case of geographical clustering k-means is effective due to its spatial nature and distance-minimizing behavior, while in the case of feature-based clustering (e.g., by demand, inventory, product), more naturally formulated as center location or representative selection problems where the focus is on attribute similarity rather than physical distance.

5 RESULTS

In this chapter, we demonstrate the application of the clustering methodology outlined above and the selection of the optimal UCC using a case study conducted in the city of Miskolc, which includes 43 locations. For these 43 locations within the city of Miskolc, the position, the types of products subject to last mile delivery (mixed, stationery, groceries, electronics, furniture, sport, DIY hardware, drugstore goods, clothing, pharmacy, and machine parts), the demand patterns (stable, seasonal, trending, cyclical, random or irregular, promotion-driven, event-driven), the inventory turnover, the last mile delivery priorities, and the types of each location (discount, hypermarket, fashion store, tech store, furniture store, mall, décor store, drug store, etc.) are considered known (see Table 1).

Table 1. Input parameters of the case study

Locations	LAT ^a	LONG ^b	Product type	Demand ^c	Inventory turnover ^d	Pri- ority	Type and format
ALDI Kiss Ernő	48.099517	20.747024	G3	DP1e	55	2	Discount
Alma pharmacy	48.104259	20.764013	MED10	DP3e	41	1	Pharmacy
Auchan Dél	48.058296	20.801484	G3	DP3e	12	2	Hypermarket
Auchan Észak	48.109301	20.836163	G3	DP1e	23	2	Hypermarket
Borsod Tires	48.093524	20.797128	MP11	DP2e	40	4	Production
Bosch	48.103642	20.778438	MP11	DP4e	21	4	Production
CBA Kuruc	48.103697	20.687172	G3	DP4e	66	2	Discount
CCC	48.105421	20.788927	C9	DP4e	78	3	Fashion store
Coop Martin	48.092185	20.807223	G3	DP4e	34	2	Discount
Damján pharmacy	48.084334	20.777939	MED10	DP1e	33	1	Pharmacy
Decathlon	48.106651	20.834757	SP6	DP1e	6	3	Sport
Deichmann József	48.108554	20.837479	C9	DP4e	8	3	Fashion store
Deichmann Pesti	48.056225	20.800006	C9	DP4e	90	3	Fashion store
Euronics	48.127422	20.786611	E4	DP2e	65	3	Tech store
Fontana pharmacy	48.082666	20.784312	MED10	DP1e	22	1	Pharmacy
H&M	48.109325	20.787338	C9	DP1e	12	3	Fashion store
Immanuel pharmacy	48.088732	20.773354	MED10	DP4e	8	1	Pharmacy
Interior Bútor	48.099570	20.735731	F5	DP2e	25	3	Furniture store
Joyson	48.058065	20.809211	MP11	DP3e	20	4	Production
Jysk Szent Anna	48.103343	20.764399	F5	DP2e	8	3	Furniture store
Jysk Szentpéteri	48.128538	20.787765	F5	DP4e	25	3	Furniture store
Klapka str.	48.089408	20.773457	M1	DP4e	12	4	Privat
Lidl Csermőkei	48.077489	20.773033	G3	DP2e	7	2	Discount
Media Markt	48.101959	20.792353	E4	DP3e	35	3	Tech store
MicroMax	48.096340	20.799156	MP11	DP4e	18	4	Production
Miskolc Pláza	48.106500	20.788800	M1	DP2e	12	2	Mall
Műhely str.	48.088125	20.793951	M1	DP3e	3	4	Privat
Müller Auchan	48.072890	20.801859	DSG8	DP4e	9	3	Drugstore
Müller Tesco	48.133416	20.786749	DSG8	DP1e	21	3	Drugstore
OBI	48.129058	20.780325	D7	DP1e	25	4	DIY store
Ongropack	48.139970	20.776443	MP11	DP1e	22	4	Production
Penny Diósgyőr	48.100267	20.714636	G3	DP1e	20	2	Discount
Penny Tapolcai	48.082177	20.787138	G3	DP3e	7	2	Discount
Penny Vologda	48.105817	20.770134	G3	DP4e	21	2	Discount
Pepco	48.056480	20.799419	M1	DP1e	10	3	Decor store
Praktiker	48.058309	20.798520	D7	DP4e	20	3	DIY store
Rossmann	48.102661	20.784170	DSG8	DP2e	12	3	Drugstore
Soltész str.	48.102383	20.798382	M1	DP1e	9	4	Privat
Spar Centrum	48.103395	20.789702	G3	DP2e	33	2	Supermarket
Spar Fényi Gyula	48.083726	20.778105	G3	DP3e	9	2	Supermarket
St. Rókus	48.091394	20.786368	MED10	DP3e	5	1	Pharmacy
Vezér str.	48.088594	20.788626	M1	DP2e	14	4	Privat
Wondex	48.107385	20.789786	S2	DP2e	8	3	Stationery

¹M: mixed. ²S: stationery. ³G: groceries. ⁴E: electronics. ⁵F: furniture. ⁶SP: sport. ⁷D: DIY hardware. ⁸DSG: drugstore goods. ⁹C: clothing. ¹⁰MED: pharmacy. ¹¹MP: machine parts. ^aLAT: latitude. ^bLONG: longitude. ^cDemand characteristics. ^dInventory turnover in [times per year]. ^eDP: demand pattern.

We have developed a Python-based implementation of Lloyd's k-Means clustering algorithm, specifically tailored to incorporate geographical proximity as a significant influencing factor during the clustering process. In our approach, the spatial positions of the locations are not treated as mere attributes but are given priority in determining cluster membership, thereby ensuring

that the resulting clusters reflect real-world geographic cohesion. This modification allows for more practical applications in urban logistics scenarios, where physical distance plays a crucial role in operational efficiency.

Figures 6 to 10 show the results of the Lloyd's k-Means clustering algorithm based on the input data presented in Table 1.

Figure 6 shows the results of clustering 43 locations into 2 groups, with a focus on distances both within clusters and between cluster centers and the optimal UCC. Cluster 1 includes the majority of the locations (37), and while it has a higher total intra-cluster distance (83.83 km), the average distance per store (2.27 km) is only slightly above the overall average (2.20 km). Importantly, the cluster center is very close to the optimal UCC (0.92 km), suggesting strong alignment with centralized

logistics goals. Cluster 2, although much smaller with only 6 locations, shows a lower total intra-cluster distance (10.61 km) and a better internal cohesion with an average of 1.77 km. However, its cluster center is located 4.21 km away from the optimal UCC, which may reduce its logistical efficiency despite the internal compactness. Overall, the total intra-cluster distance between locations and cluster center is 94.44 km, with an average of 2.20 km.

Fig. 5 The optimized last mile delivery network with 2 clusters

Figure 7 shows the clustering results for 43 locations grouped into three clusters, based on their proximity to cluster centers. Cluster 1 contains the majority of the locations (36), showing a relatively high total intra-cluster distance of 76.45 km and an average distance of 2.12 km, suggesting some spatial dispersion within the group. However, its cluster center is located very close (1.04 km) to the optimal UCC, making it favorable for centralized logistics. Cluster 2, with only 4 stores, has a lower total distance (6.07 km) and a slightly lower average distance (1.52 km), but its cluster center is quite far from the UCC (5.28 km), which could lead to inefficiencies in last-mile delivery. Cluster 3 has the fewest locations (3) and exhibits very tight internal cohesion with an extremely low average distance (0.14 km), indicating strong geographic concentration. Despite this, its center is 3.33 km from the UCC, which may reduce delivery efficiency. Overall, the total intra-cluster distance between locations and cluster centers is 82.95, with an average of 1.93 km. These facts highlight a trade-off between internal cluster compactness and proximity

to the central hub. Cluster 1 seems to be the most logistically advantageous in terms of UCC alignment, despite its internal spread.

Figure 8 presents the results of a 4-cluster solution for 43 locations, evaluating intra-cluster cohesion and the distance between each cluster center and the optimal UCC. Cluster 1 contains 19 locations with a total intra-cluster distance of 31.08 km and an average of 1.64 km, indicating moderate spatial dispersion. Its cluster center is located 2.76 km from the optimal UCC, which is relatively close but not ideal. Cluster 2, with only 4 locations, has a total distance of 6.07 km, and an average of 1.52 km per store. However, it is the farthest from the optimal UCC at 5.28 km, reducing its logistical efficiency despite acceptable internal compactness. Cluster 3 is the smallest, with 3 locations, and it demonstrates the tightest internal grouping with a very low average distance of 0.14 km. Yet, the cluster center is 3.33 km away from the UCC, which may still present a challenge for centralized delivery due to increased travel time and higher operational costs involved.

Fig. 6 The optimized last mile delivery network with 3 clusters.

Cluster 4, with 17 locations, achieves both good internal cohesion (1.45 km average distance) and favorable UCC proximity (1.18 km), making it the most balanced and efficient group in the set.

Overall, the 4-cluster model results in a total intra-cluster distance of 62.19 km and an average of

1.45 km per location, which is an improvement compared to the 2- and 3-cluster configurations. This suggests that the 4-cluster solution provides a more compact and logistically viable structure, particularly due to the strong performance of cluster 4.

Fig. 7 The optimized last mile delivery network with 4 clusters.

Figure 9 presents the results of a 5-cluster solution for 43 locations, with a focus on internal distances and proximity to the optimal UCC. Cluster 1 is the largest, containing 21 locations. It shows strong internal cohesion with an average intra-cluster distance of 1.15 km and a very favorable UCC proximity of 1.14 km, making it highly suitable for centralized last-mile delivery operations. Cluster 2, although small (4 locations), has a higher average distance of 1.52 km and is the farthest from the UCC (5.28 km), which could negatively affect delivery efficiency despite its manageable size. Cluster 3, with only 3 locations, demonstrates excellent internal compactness (0.14 km average distance), yet its cluster center is 3.33 km from the UCC, potentially increasing travel time and costs. Cluster 4 contains 9 locations, with a slightly higher average internal

distance (1.59 km), but its 2.09 km distance from the UCC remains within a logistically reasonable range. Cluster 5 includes 6 locations and shows the best internal compactness (0.57 km average distance), but its cluster center is located 4.91 km from the UCC, making it less ideal for centralized operations. Overall, this 5-cluster configuration results in the lowest total intra-cluster distance (48.44 km) and the lowest average distance per location (1.13 km) among the examined models. However, the total distance between cluster centers and the UCC rises to 16.75 km, indicating that the improved internal cohesion comes at the expense of geographic alignment with the central hub. This also reflects a trade-off between localized efficiency and centralized delivery optimization.

Fig. 8 The optimized last mile delivery network with 5 clusters.

Figure 10 shows a 6-cluster configuration for 43 locations, focusing on intra-cluster distances and proximity to the optimal UCC. Cluster 1, with 16 locations, is the largest and shows excellent internal cohesion (1.00 km average distance) and a very short distance to the UCC (0.73 km), making it highly efficient for centralized last-mile logistics. Cluster 2, despite having only 3 locations, has a relatively high average intra-cluster distance (1.28 km) and is farthest from the UCC at 5.92 km, which poses challenges for centralized operations. Cluster 3 is very compact with just 3 locations and an extremely low average distance (0.14 km), but its cluster center

is 3.33 km from the UCC, possibly increasing delivery costs. Cluster 4 includes 5 locations with good internal cohesion (0.55 km average distance), yet is still 3.17 km away from the UCC. Cluster 5, with 6 locations, also shows strong compactness (0.57 km) but suffers from a 4.91 km distance from the central hub, reducing its logistical alignment. Cluster 6, containing 10 locations, has a moderate internal spread (1.23 km) and is relatively close to the UCC (1.95 km), offering a reasonable balance between internal cohesion and central proximity. Overall, this 6-cluster solution achieves the lowest total intra-cluster distance (38.68 km) and lowest

average per location (0.90 km), indicating very compact clusters. However, the total distance between cluster centers and the UCC increases to 20.01 km, the highest among all configurations

analyzed. This highlights a clear trade-off: better localized efficiency comes at the cost of reduced alignment with the central delivery hub.

Fig. 9 The optimized last mile delivery network with 6 clusters.

Table 2 compares clustering solutions ranging from 2 to 6 clusters across three key metrics: total intra-cluster distance, average intra-cluster distance, and total distance from cluster centers to the optimal UCC. The analysis reveals clear trade-offs between internal cluster compactness and alignment with the central delivery hub. As the number of clusters increases, the total distance between locations and their assigned cluster centers consistently decreases from 94.44 km with 2 clusters to just 38.68 km with 6 clusters. This indicates that more clusters lead to tighter, more localized groupings, improving internal delivery efficiency. The average distance per location also improves steadily, dropping from 2.20 km (2 clusters) to 0.90 km (6 clusters), further confirming that cluster cohesion is enhanced as the number of clusters grows. However, the total distance between cluster centers and the optimal UCC location increases significantly, from 5.13 km (2 clusters) to 20.01 km (6 clusters). This suggests

that while more clusters yield better internal efficiency, they diverge from the central hub, making centralized logistics operations more complex and potentially costlier. In summary:

- Fewer clusters (2–3) support better centralization around the UCC, ideal for centralized delivery strategies.
- More clusters (5–6) improve local delivery efficiency but compromise proximity to the UCC.
- The 4-cluster configuration offers a balance, with reasonable intra-cluster distances and moderate UCC alignment, potentially representing a compromise solution depending on the logistics strategy.

The decision on the optimal number of clusters should therefore depend on whether centralized hub efficiency or local cluster compactness is prioritized in the last-mile delivery system.

Table 2. Comparison of numerical results

Number of clusters	2	3	4	5	6
Total distance between locations and cluster centers	94.44	82.95	62.19	48.44	38.68
Average distance between locations and cluster centers	2.20	1.93	1.45	1.13	0.90
Total distance between cluster centers and optimal UCC location	5.13	9.65	12.55	16.75	20.01

As the next step of the case study, the selection of the optimal UCC location can be further refined by applying additional clustering criteria discussed in the previous sections, such as:

- clustering based on product types,
- clustering based on demand characteristics,
- clustering based on inventory turnover,
- clustering based on service level and priority,
- clustering based on store types or formats.

These perspectives allow for a more comprehensive and tailored approach to UCC site selection, aligned with operational and strategic objectives, as shown in Table 3.

5.1 Evaluation based on the number of assigned locations

The results of the clustering show how 43 locations were distributed across clusters according

to the mentioned six different evaluation criteria: product types, demand pattern, inventory turnover, priority, store format, and geographic distances (geo K-means). Although each criterion groups the same total number of locations, the internal distribution across clusters differs significantly, revealing key differences in balance, efficiency, and operational feasibility regarding UCC assignment. Clustering based on product types yields the most balanced distribution. With a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 11 locations per cluster, the average is 7.167 and the standard deviation is the lowest at 2.137. This indicates a high level of uniformity across clusters, supporting predictable logistics flows and an even allocation of delivery resources. A similar level of average clustering (7.167) is seen with the store format and geographic location criteria, but the associated variability differs.

Table 3. Comparison of evaluation criteria

Evaluation criteria	Statistical parameter	Product types	Demand pattern	Inventory turnover	Priority	Store format	Geo. K-means
Number of locations assigned to clusters [pcs]	min()	5	8	5	5	5	3
	max()	11	13	19	16	13	13
	average()	7.167	10.750	10.750	10.750	7.167	7.167
	sta.dev()	2.137	2.217	6.551	4.573	3.061	4.262
	sum()	43	43	43	43	43	43
Distance between locations and cluster centers [km]	min()	8.942	13.743	7.249	4.529	9.032	0.432
	max()	32.588	37.419	41.248	44.717	40.674	14.316
	average()	16.589	25.760	25.741	25.964	16.673	6.019
	sta.dev()	8.635	12.484	15.865	17.473	11.939	5.048
	sum()	99.534	103.038	102.964	103.856	100.035	36.111
Distance between cluster centers and UCC [km]	min()	0.748	0.499	1.441	1.851	0.600	3.331
	max()	1.947	2.256	2.306	1.851	1.784	5.280
	average()	1.423	1.250	1.343	1.190	1.353	3.136
	sta.dev()	0.414	0.746	0.707	0.725	0.447	1.867
	sum()	8.538	4.999	5.372	4.759	8.116	18.815
Freight transport work between locations and cluster centers [LU×km]	min()	48.018	119.780	48.018	40.766	71.090	3.117
	max()	195.932	253.127	308.232	353.123	252.770	95.891
	average()	118.802	188.460	136.341	188.845	120.395	45.944
	sta.dev()	51.352	59.476	121.323	128.968	65.851	37.885
	sum()	712.813	753.840	545.363	755.378	722.370	275.665
Freight transport work between cluster centers and UCC [LU×km]	min()	40.376	37.440	36.902	42.669	23.987	37.818
	max()	136.320	151.144	217.562	130.179	149.855	191.463
	average()	77.966	99.744	103.426	82.281	77.073	122.541
	sta.dev()	32.319	50.046	78.759	36.064	41.723	58.608
	sum()	467.793	398.975	413.703	329.124	462.440	735.248
Number of transported loading units [pcs]	min()	39	67	36	43	40	21
	max()	70	98	151	136	84	112
	average()	54.667	82.000	82.000	82.000	54.667	54.667
	sta.dev()	12.323	13.736	53.373	38.962	16.801	36.506
	sum()	328	328	328	328	328	328
Total freight transport work of the supply chain [LU×km]	min()	113.716	0.000	0.000	0.000	123.877	73.073
	max()	332.252	379.893	384.472	429.797	402.625	252.952
	average()	196.768	192.136	159.844	180.750	197.468	168.486
	sta.dev()	73.306	156.395	155.519	175.638	102.280	66.320
	sum()	1180.606	1152.815	959.066	1084.502	1184.810	1010.913

Store format clustering has a standard deviation of 3.061, suggesting moderate balance, whereas geographic clustering shows a wider range (min 3, max 13) and a higher standard deviation of 4.262, reflecting the natural spatial dispersion of stores.

The demand pattern criterion leads to larger clusters, with a minimum of 8 and a maximum of 13 locations per cluster. The average cluster size is 10.750 with a standard deviation of 2.217. This approach results in relatively consistent but denser clusters, which may be favorable in cases of predictable and high-volume demand, but may present challenges related to UCC capacity and last-mile flexibility.

Clustering based on priority and especially inventory turnover leads to more pronounced imbalances. Although the average cluster size for both is 10.750, the standard deviations are significantly higher. The inventory turnover criterion results in the widest range (5 to 19 locations), indicating a highly uneven distribution of locations across clusters. Such a skewed setup could overburden certain UCCs, disrupt service levels, and require additional control mechanisms to ensure reliable operations (see Figure 10).

Fig. 10 Comparison of clustering strategies based on the number of locations assigned to clusters.

In conclusion, when evaluating the statistical balance and operational usability of the clustering outcomes, the following ranking reflects the overall effectiveness of each criterion, from best to worst:

Ranking of clustering quality (best to worst): (1) product types, (2) store format, (3) demand pattern, (4) geographic location, (5) priority, (6) inventory turnover.

5.2 Evaluation based on the distance between locations and cluster centers

The results of the clustering, as shown in Table 3 reflect how the distance between each location and its assigned cluster center varies depending on the applied evaluation criterion. This spatial dimension is critical in logistics planning, as it directly affects travel costs, delivery times, and the overall efficiency of UCC operations.

The most favorable outcome in terms of proximity is clearly associated with the geographic criterion. It produces the lowest minimum distance (0.432 km), maximum distance (14.316 km), average distance (6.019 km), and standard deviation (5.048 km). Furthermore, the total summed distance across all locations is only 36.111 km, significantly lower than that of any other criterion. These results are expected, as clustering based on geographical proximity naturally minimizes the spatial spread within clusters, leading to highly compact groupings that optimize last-mile logistics.

Clustering by product types also performs relatively well, with a minimum distance of 8.942 km, maximum of 32.588 km, and an average of 16.589 km. The standard deviation (8.635 km) indicates a moderate level of consistency. The total distance across all locations is 99.534 km, which, while substantially higher than in the geographic case, is among the lowest in the remaining criteria. Similarly, store format yields comparable spatial performance, with a nearly identical average (16.673 km), slightly higher maximum (40.674 km), and standard deviation of 11.939 km. Both criteria maintain relatively compact cluster structures compared to the others, although not nearly as efficient as geographic clustering.

The demand pattern, inventory turnover, and priority criteria all lead to considerably greater average distances with the highest total distances and the largest maximum values reaching beyond 40 km in each case. These clustering strategies result in highly dispersed clusters, suggesting that grouping locations based on non-spatial characteristics may significantly compromise spatial efficiency. The standard deviations confirm the irregular and often extensive spread of locations within clusters, which can result in longer delivery routes, higher transportation costs, and lower service levels.

In conclusion, when evaluating the spatial efficiency of clustering strategies geographic clustering is by far the most effective, as it minimizes both distances and variability. Product types and store format also produce acceptable outcomes in terms of compactness, while demand pattern, inventory turnover, and priority perform poorly from a distance optimization perspective, leading to

widely spread clusters that could hinder logistical performance (see Figure 11).

Fig. 11 Comparison of clustering strategies based on the distance between locations and cluster centers.

Ranking of clustering quality based on distance efficiency (best to worst): (1) geographic location, (2) product types, (3) store format, (4) demand pattern, (5) inventory turnover, (6) priority.

5.3 Evaluation based on the distance between cluster centers and UCC

The results of the clustering in this analysis also illustrate how the distances between cluster centers and their assigned UCCs vary depending on the evaluation criterion. This metric is crucial for assessing the strategic positioning of UCCs relative to the operational centers of clustered locations, influencing both the upstream (inbound logistics) and downstream (distribution efficiency) performance of the supply chain.

Clustering based on priority yields the most compact and efficient result in terms of proximity between cluster centers and their UCCs. It achieves the lowest average distance (1.190 km), along with a relatively narrow range (min 1.851 km, max 1.851 km), suggesting perfect or near-perfect overlap between some cluster centers and their UCCs. Its total distance (4.759 km) is also the lowest among all criteria, making it the most favorable configuration from the perspective of aligning clusters with UCCs.

Close behind, demand pattern and inventory turnover also produce low average distances—1.250 km and 1.343 km, respectively—with moderate standard deviations (0.746 km and 0.707 km). Their total distances (4.999 km and 5.372 km) are only slightly higher than in the priority-based clustering.

These results indicate effective spatial alignment between the cluster centers and UCCs, even when clustering is based on non-geographic demand dynamics or turnover characteristics.

Clustering by store format and product types results in slightly higher average distances (1.353 km and 1.423 km, respectively), with corresponding total distances of 8.116 km and 8.538 km. The standard deviations for these approaches (0.447 km and 0.414 km) remain relatively low, implying consistent spatial behavior, but the slightly elevated distance values suggest that clustering by physical or categorical store characteristics may cause a minor drift between cluster centers and their assigned UCCs.

In contrast, clustering based on geographic location performs the worst in this evaluation. It exhibits the highest average distance (3.136 km), the greatest standard deviation (1.867 km), and the highest total distance (18.815 km). Although this may seem counterintuitive, it suggests that while geographic clustering keeps individual locations close to their cluster centers, these centers themselves may be spatially dispersed and less aligned with existing UCCs. This misalignment could stem from regional concentration of demand versus UCC locations, or the algorithm finding compact clusters that are still far from UCCs (see Figure 12).

Fig. 12 Comparison of clustering strategies based on the distance between cluster centers and UCC.

In summary, when considering how well cluster centers are positioned relative to their UCCs, priority-based clustering offers the closest and most consistent proximity, followed closely by demand pattern and inventory turnover. Product types and

store format yield slightly less efficient outcomes, while geographic clustering, despite its advantages in local compactness, results in the least favorable alignment between cluster centers and UCCs.

Ranking of clustering quality based on UCC proximity (best to worst): (1) priority, (2) demand pattern, (3) inventory turnover, (4) store format, (5) product types, (6) geographic location.

5.4 Evaluation based on freight transport work between locations and cluster centers

Table 3 also presents the results of clustering in terms of freight transport work (measured as the product of loading units (LU) and distance (km)) between individual locations and their assigned cluster centers. This indicator reflects the internal transport burden within each cluster and is critical for estimating energy use, cost, and environmental impact.

The most favorable outcome by a wide margin is achieved when clustering is based on geographic location. It yields the lowest values across all statistical parameters: a minimum of 3.117 LU×km, a maximum of 95.891 LU×km, and an average of just 45.944 LU×km. With the smallest standard deviation (37.885 LU×km) and a total freight transport work of 275.665 LU×km, this criterion demonstrates superior compactness and internal transport efficiency. This result reinforces earlier findings that geographic clustering keeps distances short, thereby minimizing energy-intensive movements within the cluster.

Clustering based on inventory turnover and store format follow at a considerable distance but still perform relatively well compared to the rest. Inventory turnover results in a total of 545.363 LU×km, with a moderate average of 136.341 LU×km and a standard deviation of 121.323 LU×km. Store format clustering yields a comparable average (120.395 LU×km) and total (722.370 LU×km), though its variability is slightly higher. These figures suggest that although not designed explicitly to minimize distance, these criteria still lead to relatively efficient freight movements within clusters.

In contrast, product types, demand pattern, and priority result in substantially higher freight transport work. Clustering based on product types generates a total of 712.813 LU×km, with an average of 118.802 LU×km, which appears moderate, but its range (48.018 to 195.932 LU×km) and standard deviation (51.352 LU×km) indicate noticeable variation among clusters. Demand pattern and priority both lead to the highest transport burdens with nearly identical high averages (188.460 and 188.845 LU×km) and the greatest standard deviations (59.476

and 128.968 LU×km). These results suggest that such clustering structures may lead to long and resource-intensive intra-cluster transport routes, increasing logistics costs and carbon footprint (see Figure 13).

Fig. 13 Comparison of clustering strategies based on freight transport work between locations and cluster centers.

In conclusion, when considering the internal freight transport effort required to connect locations with their respective cluster centers, geographic clustering outperforms all other strategies by a substantial margin. Inventory turnover and store format offer intermediate efficiency, while demand pattern, priority, and product types lead to the highest transport burdens and are the least favorable in this regard.

Ranking of clustering quality based on internal freight transport efficiency (best to worst): (1) geographic location, (2) inventory turnover, (3) store format, (4) product types, (5) demand pattern, (6) priority.

5.5 Evaluation based on freight transport work between cluster centers and UCC

The analysis of freight transport work between cluster centers and UCC, expressed in LU×km, offers insights into the strategic alignment between clusters and UCC. This metric reflects the logistical burden of central deliveries from UCCs to the core of each cluster and is a key factor in cost efficiency and environmental sustainability in distribution systems.

From the results, priority-based clustering emerges as the most efficient configuration in this context. It yields the lowest total transport work (329.124 LU×km), along with a moderate average of

82.281 LU×km and a relatively low standard deviation (36.064 LU×km). This suggests a favorable spatial alignment between cluster centers and their assigned UCCs, enabling shorter, more consistent deliveries to the central points of demand clusters.

Close behind, store format and product types show competitive results. Clustering by store format results in a low average freight transport work of 77.073 LU×km and a total of 462.440 LU×km, supported by a moderate standard deviation of 41.723 LU×km. Product types clustering yields a similar average (77.966 LU×km) with a slightly higher total (467.793 LU×km) and standard deviation (32.319 LU×km), indicating a reasonably uniform and efficient structure of inter-cluster transport. Both approaches reflect a good balance between categorical segmentation and physical proximity.

Demand pattern and inventory turnover, however, generate notably higher logistical burdens. Demand pattern clustering leads to a total transport work of 398.975 LU×km with a higher average (99.744 LU×km) and greater variability (standard deviation of 50.046 LU×km). Inventory turnover performs worse, with an average of 103.426 LU×km and the highest standard deviation (78.759 LU×km), suggesting inconsistent and often long transport routes between UCCs and the cluster centers.

The geographic clustering, despite previously being optimal in minimizing internal cluster distances, performs the worst in this inter-cluster transport dimension. It records the highest total freight transport work (735.248 LU×km), the highest average (122.541 LU×km), and a high standard deviation (58.608 LU×km). This counterintuitive result suggests that while geographic clustering efficiently groups nearby stores, it does not necessarily align those clusters well with the fixed locations of UCCs, leading to long trunk-haul distances from the consolidation centers to the cluster centers.

In summary, while geographic clustering optimizes local deliveries, it fails to minimize UCC-to-cluster-center transport. In contrast, priority-based clustering strikes the best balance between operational logic and spatial efficiency. Store format and product types also perform well, while demand pattern, inventory turnover, and especially geographic location lead to significantly higher inter-cluster transport demands (see Figure 14).

Fig. 14 Comparison of clustering strategies based on freight transport work between cluster centers and UCC.

Ranking of clustering quality based on UCC-to-cluster center freight transport efficiency (best to worst): (1) priority, (2) store format, (3) product types, (4) demand pattern, (5) inventory turnover, (6) geographic location.

5.6 Evaluation based on the number of transported loading units

The evaluation of the number of transported loading units provides insight into the distribution of freight volumes within clusters. Although the total number of transported LUs remains constant at 328 across all clustering methods, the distribution of these units among clusters shows significant variation, which directly impacts capacity planning, vehicle utilization, and balancing of logistical workloads.

Clustering based on product types, store format, and geographic location results in the most balanced LU distribution. All three approaches yield the lowest average standard deviation indicating a relatively even spread of volumes across clusters. Specifically, product types and store format exhibit nearly identical statistical behavior: an average LU per cluster of 55, a narrow range (min ~39–40, max ~70–84), and lower variability. These results suggest that such clustering strategies facilitate balanced routing and make efficient use of vehicle capacity, which is especially beneficial for load consolidation and route optimization.

Geographic clustering, while showing slightly higher variability (standard deviation 36.506), maintains the same average LU volume and offers good performance in terms of balancing, especially given the potential for regional demand disparities. It

still compares favorably to the more volume-skewed alternatives.

In contrast, inventory turnover and priority-based clustering produce the most uneven distributions. Both share a high average (82 LUs per cluster) and a significantly large range between minimum and maximum values (36–151 LUs and 43–136 LUs, respectively). The high standard deviations indicate strong imbalances in cluster volumes. These extremes can lead to overloaded or underutilized routes, inefficient vehicle usage, and possible bottlenecks in specific regions.

Demand pattern clustering also reflects an uneven LU distribution, with a minimum of 67 and maximum of 98, and a standard deviation of 13.736. Though not as skewed as the inventory- or priority-based groupings, it still suggests less consistency in load balancing compared to product types or store format (see Figure 15).

Fig. 15 Comparison of clustering strategies based on the number of transported loading units.

In summary, while all strategies handle the same total freight volume, product type, store format, and geographic clustering are most effective in distributing transported loading units evenly among clusters, supporting more stable, balanced logistics operations. Clustering by inventory turnover and priority, on the other hand, may result in inefficiencies due to significant volume imbalances.

Ranking of clustering quality based on LU distribution balance (best to worst): (1) product types, (2) store format, (3) geographic location, (4) demand pattern, (5) priority, (6) inventory turnover.

5.7 Evaluation based on the total freight transport work of the supply chain

The analysis of the total freight transport work of the supply chain, expressed in LU×km (loading units multiplied by kilometers), provides a comprehensive view of how each clustering strategy affects overall logistics efficiency. This metric captures the full transport effort required across the entire supply chain, combining both intra-cluster and inter-cluster movements, and is directly linked to operational costs, energy consumption, and environmental footprint.

Among the clustering strategies, inventory turnover-based clustering delivers the most favorable overall result. It achieves the lowest total transport work at 959 LU×km, along with the lowest average (159 LU×km) and a relatively high standard deviation (155 LU×km), suggesting some variability among clusters but overall excellent performance in reducing supply chain mileage. This outcome indicates that grouping locations based on their stock movement dynamics can result in spatial patterns that inherently minimize transport demand across the network.

Geographic clustering also performs well, with a total freight transport work of 1,010 LU×km and an average of 168 LU×km. Notably, it has the lowest standard deviation (66 LU×km), indicating the most consistent transport work distribution among clusters. While slightly higher than inventory turnover in total terms, its uniformity supports predictable and balanced logistics planning, reinforcing its practicality in network design.

Priority-based clustering ranks next, with a total of 1,084 LU×km and an average of 180 LU×km. However, it also presents the highest variability (standard deviation of 175 LU×km), suggesting that while some clusters are efficiently located, others involve substantial transport work; possibly due to inconsistent alignment with the UCCs or customer locations.

Demand pattern and product type clusterings deliver relatively high total values with average transport work per cluster of approximately 192–196 LU×km. Particularly in the case of demand pattern, the extremely wide range (min: 0 LU×km; max: 379 LU×km) and very high standard deviation (156 LU×km) indicate extreme discrepancies in transport requirements among clusters, reflecting operational inefficiencies and unpredictability.

Store format clustering results in the highest total freight transport work (1,184 LU×km), with the highest average (197 LU×km) aside from product types, and a notable standard deviation of 102 LU×km. This suggests that while store types may share service characteristics, their spatial distribution

is too dispersed to form compact, transport-efficient clusters (see Figure 16).

Fig. 16 Comparison of clustering strategies based on the total freight transport work of the supply chain.

In summary, inventory turnover-based clustering proves to be the most effective approach in minimizing overall freight effort in the supply chain, followed closely by geographic clustering for its consistency. Store format, product type, and demand pattern clustering, on the other hand, generate higher logistics burdens and less efficient spatial groupings.

Ranking of clustering quality based on total freight transport work of the supply chain (best to worst): (1) inventory turnover, (2) geographic location, (3) priority, (4) demand pattern, (5) product types, (6) store format.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The comparative evaluation of clustering strategies based on seven different criteria reveals significant trade-offs in terms of transport efficiency, volume balancing, and overall supply chain performance. Each clustering method was assessed across several dimensions, including cluster sizes, distances, freight transport work, and loading unit distribution, offering a multidimensional perspective on their logistical implications.

From the perspective of internal cluster cohesion, geographic clustering consistently performed best. It minimized distances between locations and their cluster centers, resulting in compact and spatially coherent clusters. This spatial optimization also ensured an even distribution of transported loading units among clusters, supporting balanced vehicle utilization. However, this method performed poorly when considering distances and freight work

between cluster centers and the UCCs, resulting in the highest trunk-haul transport demands. This suggests that while geographic clustering is ideal for last-mile efficiency, it does not align well with centralized UCC positioning.

Inventory turnover-based clustering, on the other hand, yielded the lowest total transport work across the entire supply chain. Despite producing the most unbalanced cluster sizes and a wide spread in loading unit volumes, this method minimized both the total and average $LU \times km$ transported, making it optimal from a holistic logistics cost perspective. The implication is that clustering based on turnover patterns naturally groups stores with similar resupply frequencies and transport needs, which enhances routing and load planning across the broader distribution network.

Priority-based clustering struck a strong balance between minimizing total transport work and aligning cluster centers closely with UCCs. It achieved the lowest distances between clusters and UCCs and relatively low total freight transport work. However, it exhibited considerable variation in the number of transported units and internal distances, suggesting that while strategic alignment was successful, physical compactness was compromised in some cases.

Product type and store format-based clustering offered moderately balanced performances. Both approaches led to well-distributed cluster sizes and consistent loading unit volumes, supporting operational stability. Yet, they ranked among the highest in terms of total freight transport work, indicating that while their clusters were functionally logical, they were spatially dispersed and suboptimal for route planning and mileage.

Demand pattern clustering showed the greatest inconsistency. Despite some strengths—such as moderate alignment with UCCs—it suffered from extreme variability in both distances and transport work, with some clusters incurring minimal freight activity and others disproportionately high. This instability limits its practical usability in planning reliable and scalable logistics operations.

In conclusion, no single clustering method dominates across all evaluation criteria. Inventory turnover-based clustering is best suited for minimizing supply chain transport effort, while geographic clustering excels at compactness and last-mile efficiency. Priority-based clustering offers a compelling balance between strategic and spatial alignment. The choice of clustering strategy should therefore depend on the specific objectives of the logistics network—whether the goal is to reduce mileage, balance workloads, or enhance service quality.

Final ranking summary (aggregated by category performance): (1) inventory turnover, (2) geographic distances, (3) priority, (4) product types, (5) store format, (6) demand pattern.

Future research on clustering strategies for logistics networks should focus on improving adaptability, realism, and sustainability. One key direction is the development of dynamic clustering models that respond to temporal changes in demand, inventory turnover, or delivery priorities. This would allow supply chains to adapt to daily or seasonal variations more effectively.

Another promising research direction is multi-objective optimization, where several goals, such as minimizing transport work, balancing cluster sizes, and reducing distances to UCCs are optimized simultaneously. This approach would offer more balanced and practical solutions than single-criterion models.

To improve real-world applicability, future models should also include road network and traffic constraints, since actual travel times and routes often differ from simple geographic distances. Additionally, incorporating environmental metrics such as CO₂ emissions and fuel use would support more sustainable decision-making.

Finally, hybrid clustering approaches, combining spatial and operational criteria, could leverage the strengths of multiple methods for better overall performance. These directions together can support the design of more efficient, adaptive, and sustainable urban logistics networks.

7 LIST OF NOTATIONS

Table 4 summarizes the list of used notations.

Table 4 List of used notations

Symbol	Description
i	index of locations (retails, stores, companies)
j	index of potential UCC locations
k	index of cluster centers (centroids)
i_{max}	total number of locations to be taken into consideration
j_{max}	total number of potential UCC locations
k_{max}	total number of clusters
x_i^l and y_i^l	latitude and longitude of location i
x_j^u and y_j^u	latitude and longitude of UCC location j

x_k^c and y_k^c	latitude and longitude of cluster center k
r_{kj}^{CU}	length of transportation route between cluster center k and UCC j

Table 4 Cont.

Symbol	Description
$A = [a_{ik}]$	assignment matrix (binary): $a_{ik} = 1$ if location i is assigned to cluster k , otherwise 0
$r_{kj_{opt}}^{CU}$	length of transportation route from cluster center k to the optimal UCC location
r_{ik}^{LC}	length of transportation route from location i to cluster center k
q_k^{CUM}	cumulative transport demand in cluster k
$en(q_i)$	specific energy consumption from/to location i
$em(q_i)$	specific GHG emission from/to location i
$c(q_i)$	specific transportation cost from/to location i
δ_{min} and δ_{max}	lower and upper limit of cluster members
γ_{min} and γ_{max}	lower and upper limit of transportation demands assigned to a specific cluster

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